

THE ROLE OF COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS
INTERPRETATION

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Annotation

In every sphere a lot of people come across various difficulties such as during the translating process and everybody wants to improve and correct his or her mistakes. For that issue they need any compression for their interpretation. Thus, it is raised by Mackintosh (1995: 126), is "compression": "Compression in simultaneous is more difficult and many feel can only be attempted if the students' performance is recorded and then compared to the original. Too much attention to terminology and focusing on the words used by a student is usually counterproductive in that it distracts attention from the substance of the message. Correction is a subject on which the literature has little or nothing to say. It is virtually uncharted territory and the references are mainly anecdotal".

Keywords: correction, translation skills, simultaneous interpretation

Аннотация

В каждой сфере многие люди сталкиваются с различными трудностями, например, в процессе перевода, и каждый хочет улучшить и исправить свои ошибки. Для этого им нужно любое сжатие для их интерпретации. Таким образом, Макинтош (1995: 126) поднимает его как «сжатие»: «Сжатие при одновременном выполнении более сложно, и многие считают, что его можно попробовать, только если выступление учащихся будет записано, а затем сравнено с оригиналом. Слишком большое внимание к терминологии и сосредоточение внимания на словах, используемых учащимся, обычно приводит к обратным результатам, поскольку отвлекает внимание от сути сообщения. Исправление — это тема, по которой в литературе почти или

совсем нечего сказать. Это практически неизведанная территория, и упоминания в основном анекдотичны».

Ключевые слова: исправление, переводческие навыки, синхронный перевод

Interpreting or interpretation is the intellectual activity of facilitating oral and sign-language communication, either simultaneously or consecutively, between two or more users of different languages. Besides that interpreting demands not only profound knowledge of foreign and native languages, culture, history, geography from future professional interpreters. Interpreters are to have a number of competences which they obtain during their training.

For example, it is one of the significant strategies of simultaneous translation - speech compression. According to fundamental works in the field of methodology, theory and practice of interpreting, speech compression is one of the main linguistic features of this type of translation process. Methods A simultaneous interpreter is - as you can tell by looking at the words - someone who translates for someone in another language while the speaker speaks without interruption. This is the opposite of consecutive interpreting, because a consecutive interpreter awaits his turn and does not start speaking until the speaker allows him the time to do so.

Simultaneous interpreting is one of the most common types of interpreting, but also the most difficult one. Very few translators can do it, and not even all interpreters can do it well. Simultaneous interpreting has a number of exact advantages over consecutive interpreting:

1. Efficiency in conducting international events in which several languages are used;
2. Less expenditure of time and money: the event proceeds at its own pace regardless of the language of the speaker — this decreases the time necessary to hold the event and the material resources required;
3. Convenience for the listeners: the participants can hear the presentation in the original language without interruption for translation. It is really a very complex

process to interpret simultaneously, one that only very few interpreters can handle well. A speaker is speaking, and that speaker does not stop or pause. He keeps talking. Therefore the interpreter must do the following while the speaker is talking: listen to what the speaker is saying; translate it in his mind; render the translation in his microphone; and at the same time listen to what is being said while he is speaking himself. This necessity is defined by the fact that conditions of simultaneous translation do not always allow translating the whole content of the source text.

Firstly, the translator will find it difficult to produce the full target text if the speech tempo of the speaker is too fast.

Secondly, the speed of verbal and cognitive process of each translator is different and has its own limits.

Thirdly, fluent speech quite often affects correctness and completeness of sentences therefore adequate perception of the translation by the receptor (the translator) is broken. Simultaneous translation is the most complex of the types of interpretation, in this type of translation the translation is done using special equipment. This is a continuous speech without the interpreter being present when the speaker is speaking conveying the content to the audience is a method of interpretation. Synchronous in translation, the interpreter sits in the translation booth and the headset (earphone) listens to the speaker through. Then translate through the microphone while listening does. Delegates in the conference room listen to the main language through a headset. [Ismatullayeva N, "Problems of simultaneous translation" -4-p].

Simultaneous interpreter is also performed through gestures. From the spoken language translated into sign language. The sign language interpreters in the booth do not sit: they can see the speaker and are visible to other participants stand in the conference room. Whisper translation is synchronous such a form of translation, in which, the interpreter of the conference room sits behind the delegate who needs to be translated, not in the booth, and the speech whispers the main content in the ears of the delegate [Gafurov I " Translation theory "167 - b]. Simultaneous translation is one of the largest forms of translation characterized by high efficiency, original

text speech and translated speech. The interval between is on average 3-4 seconds. At most 10 seconds. That is why the speaker speaks incessantly guaranteed that there will be no outside influence on the speaker's opinion and does not stop talking. This makes the audience fully understand the speech allows them to reach. This is why simultaneous translation is now commonplace in the world has become a traditional method of translation. 95% of the world today simultaneous translation is used in international meetings and conferences. Therefore along with simultaneous translation has a great deal of scientific and expertise and is synchronous because it is typically used in official international conferences there are very high requirements for translation.

The following are the requirements for simultaneous translation:

Simultaneous translation from the interpreter while he is speaking in the original language a short period of time based on thematic knowledge along with listening comprehension quickly predict, comprehend information in the original language, it needs to be stored in memory and directed. However different international conference, "lightning thinking" from simultaneous interpreter at meetings will need to be able to do and have high speaking skills. International in accordance with the decision of the Association of Simultaneous Interpreters, the interpreter is a participant was able to translate only 80% of the speaker's content is calculated.

Most people are usually very fast talking always about the content of their speech text, even when they are speaking they care. On top of that, Ustak speaks in various local accents complicate. In these cases, the simultaneous interpreter moves his existing treasure trove of knowledge and are forced to act with all their might, based on their experience will be deliberately speaking slowly can take care of an interpreter not many speakers. This is extremely high on the nature of the specialist demands.

It can be concluded that, In a nutshell, simultaneous translation is among the types of translation is one of the complexes. So interpreters use this type of translation they need to pay great attention to everything in the learning process. For

instance, its history, origin, characteristics, requirements for a translator and a translator needs to study the tasks carefully. An interpreter should enrich and develop his vocabulary as well.

Used Literature:

1. Gafurov I “Translation theory ” 167 – p.
2. Ismatullayeva N, “Problems of simultaneous translation” -4p.
3. Manshuk Zh. Yeskindirova – Zhuldyz K. Alshinbayeva “Methodology of simultaneous translation: some strategies and features” -199p.
4. Zhongmei Chen “Simultaneous Interpreting: Principles and Training” -714p